

TWINNED
By Stars

D5.2 PROJECT FACTSHEET

WP5 COMMUNICATION & DISSEMINATION

TWINNEDbySTARS

**UNLOCKING THE POTENTIAL OF INNOVATION, CIRCULARITY, AND
DIGITALISATION FOR ACCELERATING NEW MARINE-BASED
ECOTOURISM, JOINT PRACTICES, AND BUSINESSES IN ORs**

Grant Agreement n° 101124900

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

VERSION HISTORY

Ver.	Date	Comments/Changes	Author/Reviewer
0.1	04/12/2023	Draft version sent to Steering Committee for comments	Sara Rebollo Ramírez
1.0	21/12/2203	Final version to be submitted after inclusion of comments from the Steering Committee	Sara Rebollo Ramírez, Silvia Pérez Palomo
2.0	09/01/2024	Updated version based on EC feedback	Sara Rebollo Ramirez

DELIVERABLE INFORMATION

Project Acronym	TWINNEDbySTARS
Project Title	Unlocking the potential of innovation, circularity, and digitalisation for accelerating new marine-based ecotourism, joint practices, and businesses in ORs
Type of action	EMFAF Project Grants
Topic	EMFAF-2023-PIA-FLAGSHIP-5-OR
Project Start Date	01/10/2023
Project Duration	36 months
Work Package	WP5 – COMMUNICATION & DISSEMINATION
Deliverable	D5.2 PROJECT FACTSHEET
Due Date	31/12/2023
Submission Date	09/01/2024
Dissemination Level ¹	PU
Deliverable Responsible	CE (CONSULTA EUROPA)
Version	2.0
Status	Final version
Author(s)	Sara Rebollo Ramírez, Silvia Pérez Palomo CE
Reviewer(s)	Steering Committee members

¹ PU= Public, SEN= Sensitive

PROJECT FACTSHEET

PROJECT FACTSHEET <i>(max 3-4 pages)</i>																									
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Project acronym and number:	TWINNEDbySTARS – 101124900																								
Summary <i>(max 100 words)</i>																									
<p>TWINNEDbySTARS (https://twinnedbystars.eu/) aims at converting European Outermost Regions (ORs) into an internationally recognized maritime ecotourism destination, which exploit benefits of tourism for marine biodiversity conservation and climate change mitigation. All this by increasing the competitiveness of the maritime tourism sector while contributing to protect marine biodiversity, preserving the cultural heritage and develop marine Astro-tourism by strengthening partnerships already in operation, capacity building and co-creation for tourism products.</p> <p>It builds on the success of previous projects in the Macaronesian region, which have built networks and methodological frameworks to codesign and tune up transformational marine eco-tourism products and activities, involving islands-based SMEs.</p>																									
Context <i>(max 100 words)</i>																									
<p>EU ORs -5M people- represent many assets: young population, extensive maritime economic zones, unique biodiversity, rich renewable energy sources, location, and climate suitable for space sciences, astrophysics activities, as well as important space infrastructure.</p> <p>Nevertheless, they face permanent constraints to their development, especially regarding the coastal and maritime tourism sector (largest Blue Economy sector in terms of gross added value, profit and employment – EC, 2019), where there is not clarity regarding the degree of physical effort, the level of specialization, the instruments, and the offerings that distinguish marine, nautical and maritime tourism industries.</p>																									
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Activities (max 100 words)

An analysis of existing cooperation networks in maritime and coastal tourism in ORs will be conducted, mapping out the actors in the quadruple helix.

Secondly, a capacity-building programme will be crafted to raise awareness and equip tourism firms and other stakeholders with tools to accelerate digital and ecological transitions to identify opportunities for open and social innovation with actors from other ORs.

Finally, the consortium will analyse available coastal and maritime tourism products and development sites in the four ORs. This data will be processed to design and implement co-creation workshops on tourism products, which will be tested with real customers.

Results achieved (max 100 words)

Main results will be:

- **Strengthening and sustaining cooperation networks** in maritime and coastal tourism within the ORs. This involves linking the quadruple helix and ensuring network homogeneity through the promotion of certifications and promoting a unified brand image.
- **Upskilling and capacity building** for tourism firms and stakeholders in coastal and maritime tourism. This includes fostering circular economy practices, facilitating digital transition, promoting networking, and encouraging innovation.
- Creating new spaces for the **co-creation of innovative products and nautical tourism experiences**. This encompasses activities such as star tourism, marine ecotourism, sustainable Atlantic crossing using trade winds, and the application of virtual reality.

Policy contribution (max 100 words)

TWINNEDbySTARS is aligned with the **EU's Integrated Maritime Policy**, aiming to foster the sustainable development of all sea-based activities and coastal regions. It aligns also with the recommendations provided in the roadmap for the decarbonisation of the **European Recreational Marine** craft sector (ESPO Environmental Report, 2021) by promoting green certifications among the tourism SMEs in the ORs. Also contributes to the **Tourism and Transport in 2020 and beyond** that underlines the role of digital transformation and sustainability by providing training to SMEs on digital skills and digital innovation to become more resilient and competitive (Blue and Digital Economy).

Synergies with other EU funding (max 100 words)

TWINNEDbySTARS builds upon the results of previous projects such as NAUTICOM, an Interreg MAC project which led to the development of a new tourism product consisting of a one-week nautical experience for the sighting of marine fauna, pelagic birds and astro-tourism across the most important natural reserves of Macaronesia and covering the islands of Madeira, Dessertas, Salvajes, the Chinijo Archipelago and Lanzarote.

Moreover, networking events and synergies have started to be created with the sister projects from the same such as eco-ROUTE, CALLMEBLUE and FISATOUR, as a way to promote cooperation among blue economy stakeholders and facilitate the convergence of tourism and sustainability.

Other (max 100 words)

Project website: <https://twinnedbystars.eu/>

PARTICIPANTS

Participants

1. **UNIVERSITY OF LAS PALMAS DE GRAN CANARIA – UNIVERSITY INSTITUTE TIDES** as the academic and research partner of the consortium, TIDES will lead WP2 and will have an important role in the development of WP3, applying its experience in high-level training in tourism from the Canary Islands and the implementation of co-creation in the generation of new tourism products.

1.1 **FCPCT-ULPGC (Fundación Canaria Parque Científico Tecnológico de la Universidad de Las Palmas de Gran Canaria)** is the Affiliated Entity (AE) to ULPGC-TIDES and will co-lead WP4. It's a link between innovative companies and research centres. It manages a compendium of basic innovation infrastructures and the incorporation of technology companies, essential for R&D&i and technological development processes. It will manage the budget for ULPGC-TIDES.

2. **CONSULTA EUROPA PROJECTS AND INNOVATION SL (CE)** will act as the technical secretariat of the project, supporting the proposal leader in the management and coordination actions included in WP4, as well as the leadership of WP5 on communication.

3. **Canary Islands Maritime Cluster (CMC)** will lead WP1 for the sustainability of the cooperation established in the framework of TWINNEDbySTARS, under its experience as leader of the Macaronesian Maritime Marine Alliance (A3M) and partner of the Nautical Cooperation Network NAUTICOM.

4. **Océano de Experiencias, S.L. (NAUTIC OCEAN)** is a travel agency specialised in nautical tourism, which also has experience in team building and events, is a sailing club and has experience in nautical training. They will lead WP3 with the generation of new spaces for co-creation of new products and new nautical tourism experiences.

5. **The Marine Sciences Technology Center CETECIMA** is a private, non-profit association, whose primary objective is to contribute to the general benefit of society by generating of technological knowledge and its application for the development and strengthening of the competitive capacity of companies in the marine and maritime sector. CETECIMA participates in the proposal as coordinator of the nautical cooperation network NAUTICOM and will mainly support the tasks of WP1.

6. **Marina de Funchal (MARINA FUNCHAL)** offers multiple support services, including water and electricity connections, fuel stations, changing rooms and sanitary facilities, nautical equipment stores, restaurants, and bars, among others. Marina Funchal participates in the proposal, as the main geographical environment that brings together the nautical companies in Madeira Island, and its main participation will be linked to the development of WP3.

7. **Associação Comercial e Industrial do Funchal – Câmara de Comércio e Indústria da Madeira (ACIF-CCIM)** represents companies operating in the Autonomous Region of Madeira in the areas of Commerce and Services, Industry and Tourism, and currently has around 800 associated companies. ACIF-CCIM participates in the proposal on the Madeira side and its main participation is linked to WP1 and WP2, being in charge of the implementation of tasks T1.3. and T2.3.

8. **Direção Regional de Políticas Marítimas (DRPM Azores)** is a public body of the Government of the Azores, belonging to the Regional Secretariat of the Sea and Fisheries that is the local competent marine environmental authority and is also the responsible department for the management of the maritime ecotourism.

9. **Collectivité Territoriale de Martinique (CTM)** is competent for tourism, development of enterprises, blue economy and marine environmental development, among others. The Territorial Collectivity of Martinique supports local entities in different forms: greening marine tourism, support for entities specializing in the protection and enhancement of the environment; the plan to renew the fishing fleet, focused on the construction of medium-sized vessels to develop deep-sea fishing, revitalizing of fishing industry with sustainable practices, etc.

10. **European Boating Industry (EBI)** is the European federation representing the leisure marine sector, i.e., boatbuilding, equipment manufacturing for boats and water sports, infrastructure developers and operators (marinas), and the wide range of nautical service providers (charter, trade, repair & maintenance, professional skippers, insurance, and financial services, etc.). They will contribute to WP5 with the report on awareness raising activities and outreach to society.

“Ocean navigation and the stars are closely linked, the Atlantic outermost regions that participate in TwinnedbyStars will take advantage of this unique experience to make coastal and maritime tourism in their regions more resilient” (CMC)

“Maritime and coastal tourism is the subsector of the Blue Economy in which there is no competition between the Atlantic outermost regions, but rather complementarity, so regional work networks and strategic alliances result in an increase in their competitiveness” (CMC)

RESULTS AND ACHIEVEMENTS

Results and achievements

Short term impact:

- Introduction of new tourism products and services.
- Establishment of eco-tourism routes.
- Creation of sustainable partnerships.

Medium term impact:

- Development of supportive policy pathways.
- Advancement in digitalisation and circular economy practices.
- Increased awareness of ORs as sustainable destinations.
- Skill enhancement for tourism sector employees.

Long-term Impact:

- Growth in start-ups, investments, and job opportunities.
- Diversification of tourism products with reduced seasonality.

PHOTOS AND VISUALS

Photos and visuals

Picture 1. Pictures of the Kickoff meeting, the site visit to *Marina Deportiva of LPGC* and stars' observation activity.